

Utilization of Market Places Through Internet Media as a Marketing Strategy for Bumdesa

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ABSTRACT: BUMDES Strategy in Improving the Economy by Utilizing MarketPlace Through Internet Media and Supporting and Inhibiting Factors in Improving the Economy by Utilizing MarketPlace Through Internet Media. The research method used is a qualitative method. The results of the study are that the utilization of Marketplace through the Internet is one of the efforts made by BUMDes to optimize innovation in order to market BUMDes products that are online-based, through marketplace applications to expand product marketing. Product marketing still uses marketplaces on social media. Supporting Factors for BUMDes Sungai Alam in Improving the Economy by Utilizing Market Placa Through Internet Media, namely Fairly good internet network access is very helpful in the marketing process using social media, such as BUMDes product promotions have been carried out on Marketplace social media on Facebook and Instagram. The inhibiting factor for BUMDES Sungai Alam is that logistics are a challenge for business actors who utilize E-Commerce in marketing and shipping goods. The payment method itself has not been determined, where transactions when shipping goods are still carried out using the Cash on Delivery (COD) method which is the consumer's choice in purchasing goods belonging to BUMDes Sungai Alam. Consumers still often cancel purchases of ordered goods, making it difficult for BUMDES Sungai Alam to develop.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Strategy *Market Place*, *Internet*, BUMDES

I. INTRODUCTION

Science and technology in today's era have been able to create prosperity and convenience in all aspects of human life. Allah has laid the outlines of science and science in the Qur'an, humans only need to dig and develop existing concepts and theories, among others as contained in QS. Ar-Rahman verse 33.

It means: "O jinn and man, if you are able to penetrate (cross) the heavens and the earth, then cross it, you cannot penetrate it except by strength."

The above verse in the past fourteen centuries has given a scientific signal to the Jinn and Man, that they have been welcomed by Allah to explore in space as long as they have the ability and strength. The power referred to here as interpreted by scholars is science and technology, this has been proven in the modern era today, with the discovery of means of transportation capable of penetrating space, nations that have made progress in the field of science and technology have repeatedly landed on the Moon, Mars, Jupiter and other planets (Sumarni, 2017).

The rapid development of information and communication technology or known as *Information and Communication Technology* (ICT) and the internet have penetrated various areas of life, including business and trade (Zaidan Johri, 2010). With the internet and ICT, the marketing and sales process can be carried out at any time without being bound by space and time. With web/internet capabilities that can transmit various forms of data such as text, graphics, images, sounds, animations, or even videos, many businesses take advantage of this technology by making *home page* to promote his business. Now almost all levels of society (especially in developed countries) are very familiar with this web, because almost any type of information can be obtained.

With the development of information and communication technology in the economic field, marketing through the internet network. The development of marketing through the internet network is very rapid. The transactions that occur are very tempting, so that they attract the interest of business people to utilize the internet as a new marketing channel. With the internet, it is possible for a small and medium-sized company to compete openly with other large companies and seize opportunities in the global market. Another attraction of marketing through the internet is the market reach that is no longer limited to a number of regions or within a country, but the whole world. This is certainly what makes a potential small company globally the same as a transnational company (Zaidan Johri, 2010).

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Technology has developed rapidly, so a media is needed that can help and provide information quickly. *Marketplace* leading to the use of digital technology in doing business (Digital Marketing). Digital marketing is also defined as marketing activities that use internet-based media (Ahmad Heru Mujianto et al., 2020).

Digital marketing is a marketing medium that is currently widely liked by the public because it strongly supports the various activities carried out. The development of technology is very beneficial for both parties, namely producers and consumers because *marketing trends* in the world have shifted from the original conventional/traditional (*offline*) to digital/modern (*online*). People now prefer to find information through Internet-based social media, so the effort that must be made is to use a digital marketing strategy by utilizing the market place on social media, this strategy in the future is more efficient because potential consumers can explore all information about products or services easily and transactions can be done at any time (*real time*).

The process of buying and selling transactions that are currently carried out uses a device using the internet network. So, the payment process and delivery of goods can be done only using electronic devices. *Marketplace* is one of the main roles in business on today's E-commerce platforms. Where, everyone does a lot of buying and selling activities by utilizing *the E-Commerce website* because it has various features and conveniences in terms of use and effectiveness in obtaining a product or service.

Marketplace is a platform where it has the task of being an intermediary between sellers and buyers to carry out the process of online product transactions. *The marketplace* or online marketplace also provides various facilities such as payment methods, estimated delivery, product selection by category, and other features.

The types of Marketplaces (*E-Commerce*) in Indonesia are Lazada Indonesia, Tokopedia, Buka Lapak, Blibli, Shopee, JD Indonesia (JD.ID), Bhinneka, Elevenia, Zalora Indonesia, Matahari Mall. For now, the most visited are Shopee, Lazada, Tokopedia, and Buka lapak, but many sellers in Indonesia are using online store sites on social media such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram to promote their merchandise.

Every company must have its own marketing strategy, both large and small companies located in urban and rural areas. Sungai Alam Village, Bengkalis District started a new business in BUMDES with a sense of optimism. The Village Head stated that based on the opportunities and potentials of Sungai Alam Village and read business opportunities that can be developed for the welfare of the community. BUMDES runs its business with the support of the Village Government and the community such as PKK and household craftsmen.

With the existence of digital marketing, promotional activities and finding a younger market by utilizing various means. Digital marketing is also not worried about being limited by geography or time.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDES)

BUMDes or Village-Owned Enterprises according to Ministerial Regulation Village, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia, Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia concerning the Establishment, Management and Management, and Dissolution of Village-Owned Enterprises, Number 4 of 2015. Village-Owned Enterprises, hereinafter referred to as BUM Desa, are business entities whose capital is wholly or most owned by the Village through direct participation derived from the Village's wealth which is separated in order to manage assets, services, and other businesses for the maximum welfare of the Village community (Ministerial Regulation Number 14 of 2015, 2015).

B. BUMDESA Strategy

Strategy of Village-Owned Enterprises according to Iyan in 2020 in the Journal of environmenta The development strategy of Village-Owned Enterprises that are very important in the development of BUMDes includes spring water sources which are important assets for the village, supporting physical infrastructure, and positive support from villagers. In addition, another key to the success of the development of BUMDes organizations is social, familial and also professionalism (Mawung & Mantikei, 2020).

C. SUPPORTING AND INHIBITING FACTORS OF BUMDES

Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, Villages can establish business entities in accordance with the potential and needs of the village(Law No. 32 of 2004, 2004). Government Regulation Number 72 of 2005 concerning Villages states that in order to increase village and community income, the village government can establish Village-Owned Enterprises in accordance with the needs and potentials of the village (Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia, 2005). Permendagri No. 39 of 2010 concerning Village-Owned Enterprises, where it states that BUMDes were established as a driving force for the village economy.

Based on laws and government regulations, this means that the formation of BUMDes is based on the needs, potential, and capacity of the village, as an effort to improve community welfare. The planning and formation of BUMDes is on the initiative of the village community. BUMDes was established based on the needs and potentials of the village which is an initiative of the

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village community. This means that the business that will be realized in the future is excavated from the desire and desire to create progress in the village community (Ibrahim, 2019).

D. Marketplace

Market Place leads to the use of digital technology in doing business (Digital Marketing). Digital marketing is also defined as marketing activities that use internet-based media (Mujianto et al., 2020).

Marketplace is a new business model that develops in line with the rapid development of information technology infrastructure. *Marketplace* It is designed to minimize complex business processes so that efficiency and effectiveness are created. With the existence of *Marketplace* Everyone can do buying and selling activities easily, quickly and cheaply because there are no limits on space, distance and time. Conventionally, the market has several roles, including facilitating transactions and providing infrastructure (Yustiani & Yunanto, 2017).

Marketplace is a platform where it has the task of being an intermediary between sellers and buyers to carry out the process of online product transactions. *The marketplace* or *online marketplace* also provides various facilities such as payment methods, estimated delivery, product selection according to categories and other features.

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The current Marketplaces are **Tokopedia, Bukalapak, Shopee, Lazada, Blibli, JD Indonesia (JD.ID), Bhinneka, Elevenia, ZALORA Indonesia, Matahari Mall, Nanupedia.co.id**

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at Sungai Alam Village-Owned Enterprises, Bengkalis District. The subject (the person who was subjected to the research) was the Management of BUMDESA Sungai Alam, Bengkalis District. By using the purposive sampling technique, which is to take data according to needs. So in this study, 10 people were taken who were involved in the management of Sungai Alam BUMDESA. There are two instruments used in this study, namely using interviews and documentation and other sources both written and unwritten.

The data analysis in this study uses qualitative descriptive techniques. Qualitative descriptive research is research that is carried out to determine the value of each variable, either one variable or more of the nature of the defendant, without making a relationship or comparison with other variables. These variables can systematically and accurately describe the population or a particular field (V. Wiratna Sujarweni, 2014).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Supporting Factors of BUMDES

Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, Villages can establish business entities in accordance with the potential and needs of the village (Law No. 32 of 2004, 2004). Government Regulation Number 72 of 2005 concerning Villages states that in order to increase village and community income, the village government can establish Village-Owned Enterprises in accordance with the needs and potentials of the village (Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia, 2005). Permendagri No. 39 of 2010 concerning Village-Owned Enterprises, where it states that BUMDes were established as a driving force for the village economy.

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The supporting and inhibiting factors of BUMDESA can also be seen as follows (Dine Meigawati, n.d.):

1. Policy Size and Purpose

The Bumdes program is fully utilized by the community, because there are still some people who do not understand the scope of the program. This is due to the lack of socialization carried out by officers to the surrounding community.

2. Resources

Resources play a very important role in the implementation of a policy. Policy implementation needs the support of resources, both human resources and non-human resources. Resources involved in the implementation of the Bumdes program are still lacking. The recruitment system of its managers is based on voluntariness. In addition, financial resources, in the Bumdes program, the available funds are still not fully able to meet the needs of the community.

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3. Characteristics of Implementing Agent

The Implementing Agent is one of the things that must be considered in an implementation. To realize BUMDes formed in a village is not an easy thing, because sometimes village communities tend to be indifferent and lack of responsibility from policy implementers will hinder the running of the program. capital and human resources are obstacles faced by BUMDes management.

4. Attitudes and Trends of Implementers

The success or failure of the performance of public policy implementation will be determined by the attitude of acceptance or rejection from the implementing (agent), not conducting socialization about BUMDes, especially the BUMDes program. There is no training event on the management of BUMDes management to support the running of BUMDes in villages. In addition, there are still Bumdes program officers who are not optimal in carrying out their work, this is due to the wages received not in accordance with expectations.

5. Inter-Organizational Communication and Implementation Activities

Humans as policy actors will need communication in carrying out a policy. communication between organizations between village officers and BUMDes operational implementing agents did not go well.

6. Economic, Social, and Political Environment

To fulfill the performance of public policy implementation in the perspective offered by Metter and Horn is the extent to which the external environment contributes to the success of the established public policy. An uncondusive social, economic, and political environment can be the culprit in the failure of policy implementation performance.

B. Marketplace

Market Place leads to the use of digital technology in doing business (Digital Marketing). Digital marketing is also defined as marketing activities that use internet-based media (Mujianto et al., 2020). The characteristics of the Internet are as follows:

1. Interactivity, the ability of technological devices to facilitate communication between individuals such as face-to-face. Communication is very interactive so that participants can communicate more accurately, effectively, and satisfactorily.
2. Demassification, messages can be exchanged to participants who are engaged in large numbers.
3. Asynchronous, communication technology has the ability to send and receive messages at the desired time for each participant.

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C. Marketing Strategy With Market Place

To develop marketing wings through cyberspace is very promising because it can promote products or services in various media spread on the internet, ranging from websites, social media, and market places. A marketplace is a wada like a traditional market where various sellers and buyers are placed. The marketplace is currently a widely visited online buying and selling medium, even consumers feel at home for a long time to explore the various products offered in the marketplace. To increase the marketing you have, you must have a marketing strategy so that the product is better known and attracts the attention of consumers. Marketing strategies that must be carried out include (Trusvation, 2020):

1. Prepare Products to Sell

Before joining the marketplace, first determine what types of products you want to sell on online buying and selling sites. In addition, what needs to be considered is the availability of stock. Don't let consumers wait too long to result in order cancellation, because it can lower the rating of took.

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In doing business online, it is greatly influenced by consumer ratings and reviews. The more responsive, the credibility of the store will increase, especially if it is able to provide quality products and have its own uniqueness.

2. Identify the Target Market

In a marketing strategy in the marketplace, after determining the type of product to sell, also identify the target market, before creating a target market, first segment the market. Anyone who is included in the target market, for example, the target market is young people aged 17-36 years, living in places that can be reached by couriers throughout Indonesia. After knowing who the target market is, the second one applies a strategy in dealing with consumers. How to behave, use contemporary language, and know the right time and time for potential consumers to visit. The third is to try not to mix it with other products that are not in line with the products you have, because it will make consumers confused about what goods are actually sold.

3. Know the Strengths and Weaknesses of Competitors

Being a new player in the marketplace, of course, you will be faced with many competitors who have already sold similar products and have great experience in the business field. Regarding marketing strategies in the marketplace, first learn the strengths of competitors to be more competitive. One of the things that is done is to buy competitor products to find out the quality of the product and what kind of service is provided to consumers. Learning from the advantages of competitors, the goal is to be able to formulate their own competitive marketing techniques. A Chinese general named Sun Zi who lived in the 500s said that if you know your strength, you are likely to win. But if you know the strength of your opponent and yourself, the chances of winning are very great. In a marketplace marketing strategy, learning from competitors is also a way to win the competition. The process of observing, imitating, and modifying is quite effective so that it can bring its products to par or even excel among competitors.

4. Kenali Marketplace

Before joining a marketplace by building an online store, first learn about some marketplace options. The goal is that the products that will be marketed are in accordance with the audience that visits each marketplace, each marketplace has its own characteristics and uniqueness. It could be that one marketplace is better known for its fashion than other marketplaces that sell more electronic goods. This is important so that the market is not mistaken in targeting consumers. After determining a marketplace that matches the product you have, you must first learn the rules of the game. Even though they have one common thread; Open a store and promote products, each marketplace has its own specifications and features.

5. Learn the Marketplace Algorithm

There are many competitors who sell similar types of products, of course the competition to be the product that ranks at the top is very tight. Because the product at the top usually has a greater potential to be purchased than a good product that is not visible at all. To become a store or product at the top of the search is the most important marketing strategy in the marketplace to win the competition. The trick is to master the marketplace algorithm.

Different marketplaces certainly have different algorithms. Just like smartphone brands, different manufactures certainly have different features even though they have the same functions and uses. This strategy can be applied when uploading products along with descriptions and photos. When writing a title, try to include relevant 'keywords' in the search field. Then when creating a product description, make it as detailed and complete as possible according to the product specifications. What they want to know is what consumers want to know. The more serious the description is, the higher the level of consumer trust will definitely increase. And no less important is the product image. The first image of consumers when visiting the marketplace is that they are happy with images that look exclusive, bright, and clear.

6. Guarantee Shopping Comfort

Providing convenience to consumers in online shopping can be meaningful, such as facilitating payment transactions, shipping processes, and returning damaged goods. Not forgetting also good communication as another form of comfort. Consumers are happy if the payment transaction and delivery service have more than one option so that it is possible to choose the cheaper and faster one. In addition, service when goods are damaged is a shopping comfort that is rarely offered.

7. Organize Products as Attractive and Concise as Possible

Not infrequently in online shopping, the products you buy are indeed of high quality, but once they reach your hands, the packaging is untidy and prone to theft. Meanwhile, consumers should be made happy with charming packaging. Making attractive product packaging certainly has a way. It's just a matter of how you want your own creation to be made. For example, carrying a vintage and rustic theme or finishing with decorations of pictures of flowers and writing. In essence, through your creative imagination, create packaging that has a certain message. In addition, it is not only useful to attract consumers to be amazed, but also try to make the packaging multifunctional when it is no longer in use. What about the use of plastic? Now there is a solution, by using bioplastic packaging to coat product packaging. The product is safe into the hands of consumers, and the environment is safe.

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D. Inhibiting and Supporting Factors Using Market Place

1. Factors Hindering Using the Marketplace

There are three challenges according to Yasunobu, Director of Rakuten Online Shopping, by Rakuten and e-commerce players in Indonesia, namely internet penetration, logistics and payment methods (Cellular, 2015).

- a. Internet access is the backbone for e-commerce to grow. Therefore, the uneven penetration of the internet to all regions of Indonesia is one of the challenges that Rakuten must face. "But currently the quality of the internet in Indonesia has begun to improve"
- b. The logistics factor is a challenge for e-commerce players to distribute their products, considering the vastness of Indonesia, making the logistics factor a challenge for e-commerce players. However, according to Yasunobu, 70 percent of Rakuten's customers are outside Jakarta.
- c. The payment method for e-commerce is not so well established where transactions during delivery of goods (Cash on Delivery = COD) are still the dominant choice of the Indonesian people. This method is widely chosen by those who are worried about fraud. Regarding this payment method, in Indonesia it is very different from developed countries where transactions using credit cards are the main choice of online buyers. Of the 250 million people in Indonesia, in 2013 alone, only the number of credit cards in circulation was only around 15 million.

2. Supporting Factors for Using the Marketplace

The high rate of e-commerce users in Indonesia is certainly due to several factors. The underlying factors of this significant development include increasing population growth, to the development of increasingly advanced technology. Here are some of the main factors that affect the growth of e-commerce in Indonesia as follows (Farah Ramadhani, 2020).

a. Population Growth Increases

The biggest factor that causes the increase in e-commerce use is the high population growth rate in Indonesia. In 2019, the middle class in Indonesia achieved an increase of 21% of the total population. This increase in population has an effect on online shopping activities. The increase in the number of transactions made on the marketplace increased by 23% from 2018 to 2019.

b. Smartphone Users Increase

The smartphone industry in Indonesia has provided the best innovations so that everyone can access the internet. This has been proven by almost 89% of the total Indonesian population has used smartphones in 2020. The number of smartphone users in Indonesia is based on current needs. The pandemic era requires school children to have supporting devices such as smartphones and laptops. Plus, the price of smartphones in Indonesia is quite affordable so that people from various classes can have it.

c. Internet Users Increase

The increase in smartphone users is directly proportional to the number of internet users. It is recorded that 70% of internet users in Indonesia use smartphones to browse the internet. In making payments in the marketplace, smartphone users dominate by almost 75%, compared to online transactions through laptops or PCs.

d. The Largest Number of Social Media Users

Generally, the purchase of goods in e-commerce is also influenced by the marketing strategy carried out by sellers on social media. Therefore, the number of social media users in Indonesia has a big influence on increasing the pace of e-commerce. Data from M-Target states that Facebook users in Indonesia have reached 122 million people and occupy the fourth country with the largest Instagram users. With so many users, it's no wonder that a lot of trading takes place on social media. The influencer phenomenon can also be a supporting factor for social media users to make transactions in certain e-commerce.

e. Financial Technology Companies Are Growing

The last factor that affects the high growth rate of e-commerce in Indonesia is the growing financial technology. It was recorded that around 66% percent of Indonesians did not have a bank account in mid-2018. However, as more e-commerce emerges, the number of bank account users and cashless transactions has increased dramatically. Data obtained from Bank Indonesia states that the total cashless transactions that occurred in 2020 reached around Rp126.95 trillion, after previously only reaching Rp47.19 trillion. This surge in the use of electronic money is what supports the rapid growth rate of the marketplace in Indonesia. Easy payment with e-money makes Indonesians prefer to shop at online stores.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The strategy of BUMDESA Sungai Alam in Improving the Economy by Utilizing Market Place Through Internet Media is the nature of marketing products produced by BUMDes and in collaboration with the community and PKK women experiencing obstacles, one of which is the lack of marketing strategies used. The marketing process is still very simple, because it is only done by word of mouth so that the target market is still within the scope of Sungai Alam Village. The factor that the product is not known by the outside public is the lack of promotion, still weak understanding of promotion, especially is still not able to develop

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a marketing strategy in the field of technology such as the use of Marketplace through the Internet. For now, BUMDes Sungai Alam already has a Village Web, which is one of the efforts made by BUMDes to optimize innovations to market online-based BUMDes products through marketplace applications to expand product marketing, but in its implementation it is still not optimal because there is still a lack of human resources in running the web, so for now the use of applications in product marketing is still using the marketplace on Facebook social media.

Factors (Inhibitors and Supporters) of BUMDESA Sungai Alam in Improving the Economy by Utilizing the Placa Market Through Internet Media, namely Internet Access, internet access in BUMDes has been very helpful in the marketing process using social media, such as the promotion of BUMDes products has been carried out on the social media Marketplace on Facebook, Instagram. BUMDes has also designed the Sungai Alam BUMDes Website to be used as a place to promote products and services produced by BUMDes. In using the marketplace as an Internet marketing strategy, it is also still an obstacle because there are still frequent interruptions in the internet network. The uneven internet in all regions of Indonesia is one of the challenges that must be faced, but for now the internet network in BUMDes Sungai Alam is quite good. Logistics Factor, The logistic factor is a challenge for business people who utilize E-Commerce in marketing and shipping goods because Indonesia consists of islands so that the delivery of goods is often hampered considering the distance traveled in delivering goods to consumers often experiences disruptions that cause delays in the delivery of goods to consumers. Payment Methods, For payment methods that are not so well established where transactions during the delivery of goods are still carried out Cash on Delivery (COD) which is the choice of consumers in purchasing goods belonging to Sungai Alam BUMDes. This payment method was chosen because many consumers are still afraid of fraud and there are also those who feel that they want to see the goods first if they are willing then the consumer will pay and if not, sometimes consumers still often cancel the purchase of the ordered goods. This is one of the problems faced by BUMDes in marketing because there are still orders that are canceled by consumers.

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